

Lead Poisoning From Non-FDA-Regulated Hemorrhoid Cream

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Abstract: Lead poisoning poses a significant health risk, particularly in the context of unregulated herbal medicines. This case report details the death of a 59-year-old woman who succumbed to complications from lead poisoning (cerebral edema and encephalopathy) following the use of an herbal cream to treat hemorrhoids. This incident highlights the dangers associated with unregulated herbal products, which can often be contaminated with harmful substances like heavy metals. Despite the perception that herbal remedies are safer and more affordable alternatives to conventional treatments, their natural appeal does not mitigate the risk of contamination. Many herbal plants can accumulate metals from their environment, exacerbating the risk of lead exposure. This case underscores the urgent need for stricter regulations and oversight in the herbal medicine industry to prevent such health hazards. Implementing stronger regulatory measures are essential to ensure that all medicinal and cosmetic products are free from harmful contaminants and to safeguard public health against the significant risks associated with lead poisoning.

Keywords: Lead poisoning; cerebral edema; hemorrhoid complication; anemia of unknown etiology; herbal medicine, heavy metal poisoning; case report

I. INTRODUCTION

Lead poisoning presents a serious health risk due to its nonspecific symptoms, such as fatigue, irritability, and headaches which can make diagnosis challenging [1]. Economically, the impact of lead poisoning is profound. Acute exposure can result in costly medical treatments and loss of productivity, while long-term exposure can lead to chronic health issues, higher healthcare costs, and diminished cognitive abilities, particularly in children [2]. Infants are especially vulnerable, as breastfeeding mothers exposed to lead can pass the toxin to their babies, causing developmental delays and other health problems [H2]. Essentially, no blood lead level can be considered safe [3, 4]. The current Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) standards, which set the threshold for environmental lead exposure blood lead level (BLL) at 40 mcg/dL, are widely considered outdated and insufficiently protective.

These standards fail to address the full scope of risks associated with lead exposure, leaving workers and communities vulnerable to its harmful effects [5]. A BLL greater than 3.5 mcg/dL is considered two standard deviations above the population average, and levels at or above 10 mcg/dL can result in lead toxicity [6, 7].

Globally, lead poisoning remains a critical health issue, with millions of children affected each year. In developing countries, high levels of lead exposure are often due to unintentional ingestion, environmental contamination, and inadequate government regulations [8, 9]. In the United States, despite significant progress in reducing lead exposure, approximately 500,000 children still have blood lead levels above the reference value established by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) [10]. This issue is particularly severe in older housing and areas with significant environmental contamination [11]. Lead poisoning affects adults as well, though it is less frequently diagnosed than in children. Adults are typically exposed to lead through occupational settings and environmental contamination [12, 13]. Lead exposure can occur through various sources, many of which are pervasive and sometimes overlooked.

One major source of lead exposure is paint, especially in older American buildings where lead-based paints are still present. This poses a significant risk primarily to children who might ingest lead dust or paint chips [14]. Some countries continue to use lead in paint, further contributing to this risk [15]. Although leaded gasoline has largely been phased out, its remnants can still

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contaminate soil and dust [9]. Lead bullets used in shooting ranges or hunting can also contaminate the environment through lead residues [16]. Lead pipes and plumbing fixtures present another risk, as they can taint drinking water. This issue was notably highlighted by the Flint, Michigan water crisis, where lead leaching into the water supply led to severe health consequences in the community [11]. Workplace exposure is a significant concern in industries like battery manufacturing and recycling, where high lead levels necessitate stringent protective measures [13]

Certain cosmetic products, especially those imported from countries with less stringent regulations, can contain lead and lead to chronic exposure risk [17]. Both illicitly and legally produced alcohol, may sometimes have lead-containing contaminants [18]. Herbal supplements, often perceived as safe due to their natural origins, can contain lead and be unsafe [19, 20]. Other imported ceramics and cookware with lead-based glazes can leach lead into food, and using recycled metal for cookware can also result in lead exposure [21]. Marijuana users may have high lead levels due to the plant's tendency to accumulate metals from the environment [22, 23]. Additionally, some cake-decorating products and lipsticks can contain lead-based pigments, posing risks through ingestion and skin absorption [17,24,25]. Finally, living near lead battery manufacturing or recycling plants, as well as artisanal gold mines, can further increase lead exposure due to environmental contamination [24, 26].

In children, lead poisoning can have severe cognitive and developmental consequences, including significant developmental delays, reduced IQ, and learning disabilities. It can contribute to impairments in attention, memory, and problem-solving skills [27]. Behaviorally, children exposed to lead may exhibit irritability, aggression, and hyperactivity, which can interfere with social interactions and academic performance [4]. Physical symptoms often include abdominal pain, constipation, fatigue, and headaches. In severe cases, lead poisoning can lead to developmental regression, seizures, and even coma [28, 29].

Similarly, in adults, lead poisoning can result in a range of serious health issues across various systems of the body. Neurologically, adults may experience memory loss, cognitive decline, and peripheral neuropathy, which manifests as numbness or tingling in the extremities [27]. Cardiovascular effects include hypertension and an increased risk of cardiovascular

diseases [30]. Gastrointestinal symptoms may involve abdominal pain, constipation, and nausea, while musculoskeletal problems can present as muscle and joint pain or weakness [31]. Additionally, lead poisoning can lead to anemia, characterized by fatigue, pallor, and shortness of breath, due to interference with hemoglobin production [27, 20]. Prolonged exposure may impair kidney function, potentially resulting in chronic kidney disease, and adversely affect reproductive health in both men and women, leading to reduced fertility and pregnancy complications [27]. Neurologically, lead poisoning can cause brain damage, behavior changes, encephalopathy, and cerebral edema [32].

Because lead poisoning often presents with nonspecific symptoms, it can be difficult to diagnose, underscoring the need for early screening and preventive measures, particularly in high-risk environments. Lead poisoning remains a significant public health concern worldwide, affecting both children and adults. While progress has been made in mitigating some sources of exposure, ongoing vigilance and updated regulations are essential to reduce risks and protect vulnerable populations from this harmful toxin.

II. CASE REPORT

To protect the identity of the patient, this case has been anonymized. A 59-year-old female with a past medical history of prediabetes was admitted to the emergency department after her husband found her experiencing seizure-like activity that morning. She had been in normal health the previous night, but suffered another seizure in the emergency department that lasted about three minutes and was subsequently started on Levetiracetam. During her most recent physical exam one week ago, her lab workup prompted a follow-up with hematology due to anemia of unknown etiology. This time, her laboratory results indicated an elevated lactate level of 9.3 mmol/L, and her urine drug screen was negative. Additional labs showed elevations in aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), and alkaline phosphatase (ALKP) while her complete blood count still showed signs of anemia (Table 1).

A brain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) revealed diffuse cytotoxic edema throughout the cortex, leading to the administration of empiric antimicrobials for meningoencephalitis and dexamethasone (Figure 1). Due to the high risk of cerebral herniation, a lumbar puncture (LP) was deferred.

Table 1: A summary of abnormal lab findings. Note the rise in blood glucose (GLUC) levels on day 2 as the patient developed diabetes insipidus.

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 5	Day 7	Day 9
WBC'S	7.7	11.8	15	25.6	9
RBC'S	3.43	3.05	2.91	3.6	2.79
HGB	9.2	8.2	7.8	10.2	7.8
HCT	29.2	25	25.1	33.7	24.8
AST	137	--	--	--	--
ALT	154	--	--	--	--
ALKP	187	--	--	--	--
LACTATE	9.3	--	--	--	--
			170		
			173		
		146	174	161	
		145	176	159	147
		140	176	150	150
NA	141	128	176	151	152
		3.6	3.3		
		3.6	3.9	4.0	
K	4	4.0	3.4	4.3	4.2
			142		
		114	148	129	
CL	105	94	149	119	121
			21		
		19	18	25	
CO2	21	20	17	22	29
			324		
		163	278	305	
GLUC	151	142	276	248	183

with mild crowding of the foramen magnum by cerebellar tonsils.

(a)

Figure 2a and 2b: The repeat brain MRI shows diffuse cerebral edema with worsening bilateral downward tonsillar herniation and vermian herniation. A new small acute infarct in the right posterior hippocampus infarct, secondary to the herniation, is observed along with chronic basal ganglia infarcts.

Figure 1: The brain MRI reveals a severe hypoxic hypoperfusion injury with global infarction and cytotoxic edema throughout the entire supratentorial and infratentorial regions, including the deep gray nuclei and brainstem. The basal cisterns are patent,

During her hospital stay, the patient developed neurogenic shock and diabetes insipidus (see Table 1). On the fourth day, a serum lead level drawn on the second day returned, showing a level greater than 200 µg/dL (see Table 2). Physicians considered various potential sources of her lead exposure, including environmental or occupational contact, accidental ingestion or inhalation of lead particles, unregulated imported cosmetics, or contaminated herbal supplements. After asking about her use of herbal medications, suspicion arose around a hemorrhoid ointment that the patient had recently purchased from Vietnam through a Facebook advertisement. Consequently, chelation therapy with oral succimer and a continuous infusion of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) was immediately initiated. Meningitis antimicrobials were discontinued on the fifth day, and dexamethasone was stopped on the sixth day. As her condition continued to deteriorate, concerns for brain death arose. After being informed, the patient’s family consented to proceed with brain death testing. A second exam and a nuclear medicine (NM) brain perfusion scan were completed on the eighth day and it shows the absence of brain perfusion (figure 3).

Figure 3. Nuclear perfusion of the brain shows the absence of brain perfusion.

Table 2: Lead blood level values after hospital admission starting from the second day. Chelation therapy was started on the fourth day once laboratory results were received. Lead urine level values on the fifth day. Lead urine level test not performed (TNP) on the sixth through ninth day.

	Day 2	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8	Day 9
LEAD BLOOD (N < 5 µg/dL)	> 200.0	--	135.6	108.6	77.8	48.5
		1079.2				
		460.5				
LEAD URINE	--	417.9	TNP	--	TNP	--
		2452.7				
LEAD/CREAT, UR QN	--	3837.5				
		3214.6	TNP	--	TNP	--

Despite aggressive management, including seizure control, treatment of cerebral edema, and chelation for severe lead poisoning, the patient passed away on the eighth day due to acute neurological complications from severe lead toxicity complicated by cerebral edema.

III. DISCUSSION

Lead poisoning causes cerebral edema and encephalopathy through several mechanisms. Lead disrupts cellular processes by inhibiting critical enzymes like delta-aminolevulinic acid dehydratase, affecting energy production and neurotransmitter synthesis [32]. It also acts directly as a neurotoxin by interfering with calcium signaling and neurotransmitter release, potentially leading to excitotoxicity and neuronal death. Additionally, lead triggers an inflammatory response in the brain, increasing the permeability of the blood-brain barrier and resulting in cerebral edema [33, 34]. The increased oxidative stress caused by lead further damages brain cells by generating free radicals and impairing antioxidant defenses. Collectively, these effects contribute to neuronal injury, cerebral edema, and the cognitive and behavioral symptoms associated with encephalopathy [33, 34].

In many developing countries, herbal medicinal products are a vital part of healthcare and traditional medicine, rooted deeply in cultural and historical practices [35]. For centuries, indigenous communities have relied on their local knowledge and cultural practices to create effective herbal formulations, whether

through formal training or informal learning [36]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 60% of the world's population depends on herbal medicine, with around 80% in developing countries relying on it as their primary healthcare [37]. Over the past three decades, the use of herbal medicinal supplements has increased substantially. Some therapies have utilized phytochemicals and their chemical analogs to develop clinically useful drugs for treating both acute and chronic conditions [35, 37].

In developed countries, herbal remedies are also gaining growing acceptance as part of a "healthier living" approach, alongside complementary and alternative medicines (CAMs), especially in regions such as the United Kingdom, Europe, Australia and North America [M38-40]. The rising popularity of herbal medicine is often based on the misconception that products derived from natural sources are inherently safer and more affordable [M37]. However, many herbal products have not been adequately tested or monitored at all, raising serious public health concerns. The lack of regulation in herbal medicinal products can result in limited knowledge of their potential adverse side effects, contraindications, and the safest and most effective therapies [35, 40]. In addition, poor quality control, inadequate labeling, and insufficient patient information further compromises consumer safety [41].

In this case, the patient succumbed to severe lead poisoning shortly after using a Vietnamese herbal ointment, Cao Bôi Trĩ Cây Thầu Dầu (Castor Oil Hemorrhoid Extract), which was promoted for the treatment of hemorrhoids via intra-rectal application (see Figure 4) [42]. She had purchased the product on Facebook and had it mailed to the United States (US) by an acquaintance in Vietnam. It is not clear whether or not this ointment can be physically bought from unregulated marketplaces in the US [43]. However, it remains available for purchase online on Lazada, one of the leading eCommerce platforms in Southeast Asia, and is still actively advertised on several Facebook pages and private groups [46-49]. Testing by the California Department of Public Health (CDPH) revealed that the hemorrhoid ointment contained 4% lead (39,000 ppm), a highly lethal concentration [44-45]. Even minimal lead exposure can be harmful and potentially lead to illness or death; thus, it is advised to avoid products likely to contain lead, especially imported items from other countries with inadequate lead testing standards [50].

Several herbal supplements are known to contain lead, including *Ba-baw-san* (Chinese herbal remedy for colic pain), *Daw Tway* (digestive aid used in Thailand and Myanmar), *Greta and Azarcon* (Hispanic traditional medicines for digestive issues), *Ghasard* (Indian folk medicine), and *Kajal* (eye care product used in Africa and the Middle East) [51]. Many traditional medicines may contain herbs, metals, minerals, or animal products believed to treat certain ailments. However, during the process of grinding, coloring, or packaging, lead or other heavy metals can sometimes be unintentionally mixed into these products [50].

Figure 4. Cao Bôi Trĩ Cây Thầu Dầu, a Vietnamese hemorrhoid ointment. Photo credit: California Department of Public Health

This increasing use of herbal products for self-medication is often driven by various factors. Patients may sometimes feel uncomfortable bringing up their medical conditions with a healthcare provider, fear a lack of confidentiality or misdiagnosis, or may not have enough time to see a doctor, leading them to seek alternative treatments [35, 51]. Many of the risks associated with using traditional and herbal medicines come from their classification as dietary supplements or foods in numerous countries. This classification can result in less rigorous quality control, safety testing, or production standards before the products are marketed [52]. Such gaps in regulation pose significant public health concerns for both the general population and national health authorities. In response to the growing popularity of herbal medicines, particularly in developed

countries, the World Health Organization (WHO) has advocated for stronger quality assurance measures.

These measures include pushing for national quality specifications and standards for herbal products, enforcing good manufacturing practices and improving labeling and licensing procedures for the production, importing, and marketing of these products in countries where herbal medicines are regulated [35, 53]. However, to better protect public health, it is essential to adopt a more proactive approach by standardizing regulatory policies globally and ensuring that all herbal products on the market are safe for consumers and meet quality standards.

IV. CONCLUSION

Lead poisoning remains a critical global public health issue, impacting millions through various environmental and consumer-related sources. This concern is particularly pronounced for women due to the presence of lead in many commonly used cosmetic products such as lipsticks and makeup powders, which can lead to chronic exposure and associated health risks. Additionally, the widespread use of herbal medicine, often perceived as a safer and more affordable alternative to conventional treatments, poses its own set of challenges. Despite its natural appeal, the unregulated nature of the herbal medicine industry means contamination with heavy metals, including lead, is not uncommon. Many herbal plants can absorb metals from their environment, further increasing the risk of lead exposure.

The combination of these factors underscores the need for stricter regulations and oversight to ensure that all products—whether cosmetic, medicinal, or otherwise—are free from harmful contaminants. In the medical field, educating and training healthcare providers about the use of herbal medicines and their potential effects on patient health can raise awareness of how these products are being used. With this knowledge, healthcare providers can play a critical role in monitoring the safety of herbal medicine use and preventing adverse outcomes by informing their patients about the risks and benefits of herbal products. Additionally, the potential use of AI can help speed up diagnosis and educate the community about the dangers of lead exposure,

ultimately aiding in the prevention of similar tragedies in the future [54].

V. REFERENCES

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where X , Y , and Z are the coordinates of the 3D point cloud; d denotes the disparity; B denotes the baseline distance of the stereo camera; u and v are the coordinates of the depth image; c_x and c_y are the coordinates of the center of the optical axis; and f denotes the focal length. Examples of the generated point clouds are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

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